

The Attitudes of Teachers Toward Professional Ethics in The Light of Technological Developments and Its Impact On Behavioral Values of Primary School Students in General Education in The State of Kuwait: A Field Study

اتجاهات المعلمين نحو أخلاقيات المهنة في ضوء التطورات التكنولوجية وأثرها في القيم السلوكية لدى طلبة المرحلة الابتدائية في التعليم العام بدولة الكويت: دراسة ميدانية

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Abstract:

The study aimed to identify the attitudes of teachers in the primary stage of public schools in the State of Kuwait towards the ethics of the profession in the light of the contemporary technological developments, and to answer the study questions. The study sample was chosen the teaching staffs (male and female teachers) in the elementary schools of general education in the six governorates of the State of Kuwait whereby from each governorate two schools are selected; one for boys and one for girls. Hence, the sample size is 1,200 teachers divided into the number of (713) teachers, with a percentage of (59, 42), and the number of (487) female teachers, with a percentage of (40,58) out of a total of 1270 male and female teachers.

The results reveal that the teachers' attitudes towards establishing ethics in the profession need more support, especially in light of the rapid technological evolution and the challenges faced by the teachers in using such technologies. The study recommends the solidification of the ethics of the public education professionals in the State of Kuwait in the light of contemporary technological innovations; training and qualification of primary school teachers in general education in Kuwait to meet the challenges of the contemporary technological revolution; promotion of the teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the teaching profession; analysis of the attitudes of primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait towards using technology and building a strategic vision to enhance employment; review and evaluation of practices and attitudes towards professional ethics within primary schools in primary education in the state of Kuwait.

Key words: Ethics; technology innovations, attitudes of teachers in government schools; public education, primary Education; State of Kuwait.

Introduction:

Professional ethics in the field of education is an important axis to the success of any educational effort that aims to reform the system. Education is not information that teaches learning skills or practical professions but rather it is basically a great value building that builds generations that lead nations and embrace civilizations. The fact is that education with its ethics is what promotes nations and stimulates

their cognitive, intellectual and cultural coordination. Through it, new information and knowledge are transformed into a network of daily actions practiced by individuals in a society to eventually adapt to a highly civilized entity.

In fact, the link between ethics of the profession and contemporary technologies has become an important matter. Education in light of the contemporary technological evolution is surrounded by a technological fence that requires decision makers to adhere carefully with such requirements in order to achieve the difficult equation, which is preserving the original values and keep pace with the modern technology.

Teachers in any educational system are the practitioners adhering to ethics, values, and methodical behaviors that determine the nature of the relationship between them and their students in the context of ideological and social values based on dialogue and depends on the mechanisms of sound communication that would make within the educational classroom an atmosphere full of meaningful dialogue that ultimately achieves quality Education.(Gomaa,2015).

The importance of the study:

- 1- The importance of the role of teachers in establishing professional ethics inside schools in general, and particularly in the primary schools in the State of Kuwait in the context of changing attitudes of students towards technological tools, which may negatively affect the moral and national value system they have.
- 2- The importance of conducting a survey of teachers' attitudes towards anchoring ethics in contemporary technology.
- 3- Lack of sufficient similar studies in this field.

Purpose of the study:

- 1- To know the attitudes of teachers towards the ethical behavior of primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait.
- 2- To know the aspects of technological innovations and their impact on the ethics of primary school pupils and on the general education in the State of Kuwait.

The study Problem:

Due to increase in knowledge in the field of behavioral and educational sciences during the past three decades, the impact of technological developments spread across Arab societies in general and in the Kuwaiti society in particular. The openness of young people towards the use of technology has also increased.

- 1- Accordingly, the study problem can be formulated in the following main questions what is the effect of technological innovations on the moral values of primary school pupils in public education in the State of Kuwait?

- 2- What are the attitudes of teachers towards the impact of technological innovations on the ethics of primary school pupils in public education in the State of Kuwait?
- 3- How can the positive attitudes of teachers be strengthened and negatives be eliminated towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in the light of technological innovations and their impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait?

The study undertakes a field study on the attitudes of teachers in the State of Kuwait towards their professional ethics in the field of education in light of the technological developments in the State, and how such developments impact the primary school pupils in the general educations.

Scope of the study:

The study was applied to a sample of the teaching staffs (male and female teachers) in the elementary schools of general education in the six governorates of the State of Kuwait.

Terminologies of study:

1-Ethics of the teaching profession:

Flih & Saki (2005) define it as: "Those agreed value-based and debt-based frameworks that all workers in the teaching profession adhere to, taking into account the legal, social and humanitarian controls of these institutions in an interactive framework that achieves effective communication within educational institutions."

2-Technological innovations:

Dagher,(2012) defines it as: "Those diverse innovations on the local, regional and global scenes that are an expression of contemporary civilizational development in technologies of all kinds, which represents a strong influence in making a targeted impact on the behavior of individuals and groups."

This research defines "technological innovations" and their relationship to professional ethics as the group of contemporary technological media that is used within educational institutions and their social, moral and scientific implications that can achieve a qualitative leap in the field of education, its ethics and patterns through good interaction between teachers and students.

Theoretical framework of the study:

First: Professional ethics in the field of education with respect to teachers.

Al-Harbi (2017), indicated that a teacher must display a set of moral values within the classroom such as: Honesty and its practice in word, deed and behavior within the classroom and to set an example for its students. - Justice, impartiality and support for equal opportunities her students within a framework of self-control for her conscience, patience and compassion in dealing with his students and avoiding violence and cruelty.

According to Al-Azmi and Al-Rumidy (2011), teachers have an important role in developing values and ethics within the classroom, for instance; embedding the values of students through realistic practice; supporting the system of national values to instill in the hearts of young people; confronting the fierce

waves of attack targeting Kuwaiti society; promoting loyalty and belonging in the hearts of young adults; as well as enhancing the ability to face the technological developments and its negative effects on the value system in Kuwaiti society.

Othman Muhammad Al-Manea,(2019) studied the level of the implications of Islamic educational thoughts on the Charter of Ethics for the Saudi Education Profession by using the content analysis methodology on an intentional sample of the most prominent Islamic educational thought books of Bin Sahnoun, Al-Qabsi, Bin Abd Al-Bar, Bin Jama'ah, and Al-Ghazali , The results of the study showed the abundance of Islamic educational thought in teacher ethics..

Through the experience of the researcher and his communication with many primary school pupils in general education and the teachers of these schools and some principals, a set of facts can be pointed out here:

The researcher sees the importance of ethics in the teaching profession. Kuwait is an Arab country that derives its cultural and moral depth from the depth of the Arab nation to which Kuwait belongs, and therefore the ethics of teachers with regard to the teaching profession is a well-established ethic that must emerge from its theoretical framework into a practical and applied framework within the institutions of educational Public schools, especially primary schools in the State of Kuwait. The researcher also notes that the system of the above mentioned values within public education schools in the State of Kuwait began to be negatively affected by the new technological openness. Hence, the importance of this study.

The contemporary value gap in Kuwaiti society indicates that educational institutions and colleges of education are also not prepared to adequately confront this phenomenon. Teachers' attitudes toward these values are mixed between those keen on values, tough in their defense, and those that are indifferent to values and open to the innovations of the times. The religious dimension of primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait needs a comprehensive review, confirming the importance of adhering to the religion and its fundamentals as an important input and basis for preserving the Kuwaiti identity and maintaining the cohesion of the state and the integrity of young thoughts .

Second: Contemporary technological innovations and their impact on the value system in general schools in Kuwait :

Contemporary technologies vary with regard to the use of the educational computer, the global information network, and social media of all kinds, especially in this new age in which primitive educational methods became extinct and was replaced by what is known as advanced technological means (the era of scientific openness), which became an integral part of the educational process and the teaching process using technological innovations philosophy in order to achieve its goals (Shady, 2012).

A) Properties of technological innovations: Technological innovations have several characteristics that control the quality of educational aids and their suitability for the educational situations. Among the most important of these characteristics are:

1- **Suspense:** The element of suspense in technological innovations is a very important factor in its success. Technological suspense is the responsibility of the designer and producer. Consequently it has

an impact on the ethical values and behaviors of primary school pupils in general education

2- **Convenience:** It refers to the extent of the technical suitability of the level of linguistic, cognitive, emotional and physical education or its relevance to the learner's language and previous experience.

3- **Regulation:** It is intended to regulate the use of technology as it is not permissible to use the technology in a chaotic manner, because that creates dispersion, as the regulation in displaying the technology must suit the educational content

B) Standards for the use of technological innovations in the teaching process:

Al-Zoghbi (2003), indicates several criteria that teachers who use technology must observe, namely;

- The standard on the extent to which the technique is appropriate for pupil's physical, emotional, and cognitive characteristics: Teachers must employ technology and relate its content to pupils' thoughts, activities, and previous experience.
- The standard of the curriculum for a subject that usually consists of goals: Teachers here should employ technology in a manner that suits the content of the curricula, their teaching activities, curriculum outputs (learning outcomes) and the ability to achieve educational goals.

As per the researcher's experience and presence in the general schools, especially primary schools, dependence on technological media through electronic laboratories, employing technologies and using the Internet in schools and linking them to national and global information sources has become an important matter through which the State of Kuwait aims to keep up with the world in teaching. Therefore, the researcher believes that the employment of technological innovations in the educational process is very important for the following reasons:

- Consulting students' interests and satisfying their needs for education as the students receive, through the use of different educational techniques, some new experiences that boost their interests in order to achieve their goals.

- Increasing the student's experience, which makes them more prepared to teach on some academic subjects through various school techniques that create the necessary experiences for the student and make him more willing to learn.
- Helping to diversify learning styles in order to address individual differences among learners. The relationship between the teacher and the learner is strengthened in a new, civilized, and interactive framework that carries innovative and geographical challenges.

The research here tries to determine in a critical and analytical framework the extent of the influence of contemporary techniques on general education students and the ability of teachers to respond to these techniques that would establish the general trend towards improving education in Kuwait and towards establishing new rules for a purposeful educational position while ensuring that the original moral values are preserved for students in the Kuwaiti society.

Previous studies:

First: Studies in the field of professional ethics and teacher attitudes towards it .

Al-Ghassani,(2009) examined the charter of ethics for the education profession in the sultanate of Oman. He reviewed the concept of ethics and the most important Islamic values for the teaching profession, and the ethics of teachers and learners in Islam. The study presented a charter dealing with four main areas for the advancement of the ethics of the profession namely; the field of educational systems , the field of colleagues in the profession.

Alwanayah and kalbani (2011) dealt with the concept of teaching ethics and reviewed the role of professional ethics in establishing the quality of education and how we can employ new ethics to keep pace with the trends and how school principals, students and teachers can adhere to the general ethical framework that would advance the contemporary teaching system.

AlLewaniya and Al-Kalbania,(2011) showed its results the importance of the concept of ethics in the teaching profession and the role of professional ethics in establishing the quality of education, how we can employ ethics in a new employment that keeps pace with the times, and how school administrators, students and teachers can adhere to the general moral framework that would advance the contemporary teaching system.

Heilbron and Doly,(2018) studied the ethics of school education and ways to appreciate services in England. The study showed the importance of training teachers and enabling them to practice sound ethical values through prepared and qualified courses; how to spread professional ethics among teachers; the mechanisms to address the obstacles that prevent this and achieve; the alignment between student and teacher goals and the established ethical values.

Second: Studies dealing with the innovations of technology in education:

Majdi Mohammad Rashid's study, Hinnawi(2018) aimed to identify the reality of students' use of self-organized e-learning and to identify the students' attitudes towards this type of e-learning at Al-Quds University. The results showed that all students had at least one or more devices that enabled them to learn through self-organized e-learning, and the smartphone was the most popular device among students at 87%. The results also revealed that students not only need more awareness of some practical aspects including guidance and supervision, but they are also required to interact actively with e-mails on the university's academic portal. Moreover, the results showed that the students' attitudes toward self-organized e-learning were high either on the overall score of the questionnaire or on all elements of the questionnaire. In addition to the presence of statistically significant differences between students' attitudes due to the frequent use variables of the "help and guidance" emails, the frequent use of the e-course page, and the main source of learning used by students, the author recommended the use of the e-learning style organized for students because of its importance to them.

Nouasiriya (2018), studied the use educational technology in the educational process because of its importance within educational institutions. The results of which showed that educational technology is of great importance, especially in the field of education and learning, as education was the key from which all societies entered modernity and contemporary whatever its nature, given the challenges and pressures that faced the educational process, especially during the second half of the twentieth century,

as a result of the remarkable population increase. On the global level, the explosion of knowledge, the expansion of the scope of education, the revolution in technology and communications, and the associated dimensions and variables pressed educational professions and educational institutions to undertake more effective steps to accept all the changes and keep pace with contemporary challenges. among the most important means that the institutions resorted to Educational use of modern technologies for educational technology.

Abu Latifa,(2012) examined the availability of educational techniques used in the teaching of Islamic education books for the intermediate basic stage and the degree of usage by male and female teachers in Tafila Governorate - Jordan. The results showed that the interaction with the techniques is very good to a tangible degree and the study recommended to support the trend towards employing the technologies in all curricula. In this study, we endeavor to evaluate the reality of the use of technologies in the educational institutions through a secondary case study in the city of Bordj Bou Arreridj.

Commentary on previous studies:

Through a review of previous studies, the following is noted:

- Some studies emphasized the importance of establishing the ethics of the profession through a binding ethical charter, such as a study

Al-Ghassani(2009),which affirmed that the ethics of teachers with each other and the foundations of mutual respect based interaction, their ethics in respecting their students and dealing with them according to specific controls, their ethics with administration and respecting the regulations and laws governing work and teachers 'ethics with parents and listening to them).

--Some studies (Al-Enezi, 2007; Al-Khatib and Ismail, 2011; Abu Latifa, 2012) emphasized the importance of employing technological tools in the teaching profession and the importance of teaching programs turning into contemporary electronic packages within the framework of a sound scientific method and framework that achieves both quality and enjoyment in education at the same time.

Research Methodology

Study Population:

The study population of this study are the 1270 teaching staff working in the elementary schools (boys and girls) in general education in the State of Kuwait. The success of any field study to achieve its objectives depends largely on the good selection of the sample. A sample that represents well its indigenous population helps in obtaining correct and clear results. It is difficult for the researcher, when studying a phenomenon in a particular society, to study all members of that community. It is not feasible to observe all these individuals under controlled conditions, so the researcher usually selects a representative sample from the population. The researcher tries to make all the attributes and characteristics available in the sample generalizable to the overall population while taking into account the limits of time, effort, and possibilities available to him.

Sampling**Size:**

In order to ensure the validity and reliability of the sample size, a stratified random sample was chosen. The selected sample size compose of 1,200 teachers in public education schools in the State of Kuwait, of which 713 or 59,42% are male and 487 or 40,58% are female. From each out of the six governorates in the State of Kuwait, teachers from both the boys and girls schools are target and are distributed 1200 questionnaires, making the distribution rate roughly 94.5% (1200/1270). Such sample size can arguably represent the study population adequately considering the extremely large size of the sample. The following frequency table presents the participants on various dimensions:

Table (1) Statement of the questionnaires distributed among the respondents

Variables		Total	percentage
Sex	Male	713	59,42
	female	487	40,58
Years of Experience	< 5 Years	490	40,83
	5 – 10 Years	405	33,75
	> 5 Years	305	25,42
Bachelor of Science	Degree	870	72,5
	Master	200	16,67
	PhD	130	10,83

the sample	Distributed copies	Recovered copies	Wastage	Unlikely	The good
Teachers	800	753	47	40	713
Parameters	500	517	33	30	487

Total	1350	1270	80	70	1200
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Table (2) Statement of the questionnaires distributed among the respondents

Research Design

The study aims to shed light on the attitudes of teachers towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in the light of technology developments and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait. Considering the objectives this study seeks to achieve, a field study is conducted to reach the participants and collect their views as done by previous researchers.

Research Approach

The researcher uses the descriptive analytical approach, as it is appropriate to the nature of the study, which relied on scientific efforts in the field of professional ethics for teachers in light of the innovations of technology in the educational process. This approach relates to describing the nature of the study, analyzing its data, and clarifying the relationship between its components.

Data

There are many tools that researchers use to obtain information and data related to a specific subject, and the questionnaire is one of the tools used by educational researchers on a large scale to obtain facts about the conditions and methods already in place (Van Dalen, 2010), and used in the study of many professions, trends and types of activities (Melhem, 2006).

Collection

Questionnaire Building:

The researcher followed the following steps in building the questionnaires:

- * Analyzing the data and information obtained by reviewing the literature on education in the field of teaching ethics, analyzing previous studies therein, and interviews with some specialists in this matter.
- * When formulating expressions, the researcher takes into account that they are objective in meaning and simple in their language, so that only the intended meaning is understood, in order to achieve the goal for which they were set.
- * Phrases are placed in a logical sequence to assist participants maintain their attention in the proper order of response.

Drafting the initial image of the questionnaire *

Procedures for applying the Questionnaire.

The procedures for preparing and implementing the questionnaire included several procedures, namely:

- Preparing the study tool and verifying its validity and reliability.
- Surveying the study population, and selecting the specified random sample.
- Distributing the questionnaire to the participants.
- Sorting returned forms, and excluding the invalid from them.
- Statistical data processing, extracting results, presenting, discussing, and extracting recommendations.

The Stability and Reliability of the Questionnaire:

The stability of the questionnaire was calculated using the equation Alpha of Cronbach where the mathematical value of the coefficient of stability (0.75) confirmed the existence of a high degree of stability in the questionnaire as a whole, and the possibility of dealing with the questionnaire with a high degree of confidence.

The tool succeeds in measuring what it was set to measure and does not measure anything else, and this relates to the extent to which we reach an accurate prediction of the degree that the examiner gets (Abu Hatab, et al., 2008). In order to ascertain the validity of the tool of this study, the first image of the scale was presented to a group of specialized faculty members to determine whether the tool measures what it was actually prepared to measure, and can achieve the goals of the study or whether it requires some adjustments, as well as to seek their opinions.

Based on the comments of the arbitrators on the axes of the scale, some phrases were reformulated and new phrases were added. Thus, the accuracy of the scale was confirmed by the agreement of most arbitrators on the validity of its terms. To calculate the validity, the following methods were used:

Verification of the arbitrators : The researcher relied on the veracity of the arbitrators to verify the validity of the questionnaire, by presenting it in its initial form to a group of professors of the Faculties

of Education with the purpose of judging the following :

- Each phrase belongs to the axis it is under.
- Appropriateness of phrases.
- Accurate phrasing.
- Adding, deleting or replacing what they deem appropriate from inappropriate expressions - Can this be shortened without disturbing the meaning?

Table (3) shows the results of the (Alpha Cronbach) test to measure the reliability and validity of the scale.

Themes of the questionnaire	Number of phrases	Alpha Kronbach coefficient	Self honesty
The first axis: Attitudes of teachers in primary schools in general education in the State of Kuwait towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education.	9	0,835	0,914
The second axis: the impact of technology innovations on the value system within primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait.	10	0,887	0,942
The third axis: Requirements for supporting teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the education profession in light of the developments in educational technology and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait.	9	0,825	0,908
The questionnaire as a whole	28	0,843	0,918

Application of the Questionnaires

The researcher applied the questionnaire in its final form to the target sample. In general, the participants were cooperative and were impressed with the study..

Statistical Tool

The statistical method used in analyzing the results involved using the SPSS system, where corresponding frequency and percentage for each phrase are calculated.

$$\text{Percentage} = (\text{frequency} / \text{number}) \times 100^*$$

$$\text{Identify the significance level using } Ca^2 = \text{Maj} (v - v) ^2 / v^*$$

Where (sum = the sum, v = the observed frequency, v = the expected frequency.)

* The statistical Ca2 was calculated at the degrees of freedom calculated by the following relationship

$$\text{Freedom degrees} = \text{number of alternatives} - 1.$$

Calculating the relative weight to determine the degree of response.*

Outcome Analysis and Interpretation Methods

The results of the field study were analyzed and interpreted where the responses of each phrase were analyzed on the basis that each question has several responses: always - often - sometimes - rarely - not correct .

In this topic, the opinions of the study sample are analyzed. Repeats, percentages, relative weights and "K2" test were used according to the following Likert scale for the following

: 4: Five-Year Likert Scale Table

The opinion	Strongly high	High	Medium	Low	Severely low
	Strongly Agree	OK	To some extent	not agree	Strongly Disagree
	Always	frequently	Sometimes	Scarcely	not correct
The score corresponding to the response	5	4	3	2	1
Relative weight	)4,20-5(	3.40) -4,19(	2.60) -3,39(	1.80) -2,59(	- 1)1,79(

Study Questionnaires:

Below are the questionnaire axes and the corresponding responses that are analyzed and discussed.

Axes1: The trend of male and female teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in the light of technology developments and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait .

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of the Questionnaire Axes 1

variable	the number	The average	standard deviation	Class
Ethics of the profession in the field of education in the light of technology developments and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait	1200	1,90	380	Low

As per table 5, male and female teachers have shown a negative trend towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in light of technology innovations and their impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait as the arithmetic average is 1.90 indicating a low-grade average. This can be detailed in table 6 below.

Table 6 : Responses to Questionnaire Axes 1

Attitudes of male and female teachers towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in the light of technology developments and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait	the number	percentage
Strongly high	84	7%
High	96	8%
Medium	233	19,42%
Low	680	56,67%
Severely low	107	8,92%

As illustrated in table 6, the largest number of the participants representing 56.67% indicated that the awareness of teachers towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education in light of innovation technology and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait is low whereas only 7% of the participants showed strongly high awareness towards the subject. This further signifies the finding in table 5.

Axes 2: The attitudes of teachers in primary schools in general education in the State of Kuwait towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education.

Table 7: Responses to Questionnaire Axes 2

m	Phrase	Strongly high	High	Medium	Low	Very low	K2	Significance level	Weighted average	Direction	Relative weight
1	Teachers believe in the importance of employing ethics within primary education institutions	60	200	260	310	370	4,432	001,0	2,4	Low	48%
		5%	16,7%	21,7%	52,8%	30,8%					
2	Teachers support students' attitudes toward embedding values	70	130	160	350	490	7,202	001,0	2,12	Low	42%
		5,8%	10,8%	13,3%	29,6%	40,8%					
3	Teachers advocate for indigenous values within institutions to meet contemporary challenges	130	190	250	280	350	3,81	001,0	2,57	Medium	51%
		10,8%	15,8%	20,8%	23,3%	29,6%					
4	Teachers employ ethics from teaching courses	110	140	170	370	410	8,679	001,0	2,31	Medium	46%
		9,2%	11,7%	14,7%	30,8%	34,2%					
5	Teachers practically apply values by interacting with their students.	140	180	230	290	360	2,38	001,0	2,55	Low	51%
		11,7%	15%	19,2%	24,2%	30%					
6	Teachers instruct their pupils to demonstrate ethics in primary schools	40	40	110	470	540	3,473	001,0	1,82	Low	36%
		3,3%	3,3%	9,2%	39,2%	45%					

7	Teachers use reward and punishment to establish values within schools	-	30	170	550	450	11,12	001.0	1,82	Low	36%
		-	2,5%	14,7%	45,8%	37,5%					
8	In schools, teachers renew their value framework to keep up with contemporary challenges	-	310	80	400	410		001,0	2.25	Low	45%
		-	20.8%	6,7%	33,3%	34,2%					
9	Teachers discuss with their students about analyzing issues of value dimensions within schools	120	170	250	310	350		001,0	2,5	Low	50%
		10%	14,7%	20,8%	25,8%	29,2%					

Table (7) shows the results of the "K2" test to indicate the differences between the opinions of the study participants on the second questionnaire regarding the attitudes of teachers in primary schools in general education in the State of Kuwait towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education, where the values of "K2" ranged between (12,38 - 381) and all of them are indicative at the level of significance (0.001). This means that there are statistically significant differences between the opinions of the Individuals of the study sample. Yet, the Individuals of the study sample agreed that the teachers defend the authentic values within institutions to face contemporary challenges with a relative weight of 51% in a medium direction.

The relative weight of the statement "Teachers use the reward and punishment method to establish values within schools" is 36%, which is low. The relative weight of these phrases ranged between (82,1) and (57,2), which is low, indicating that the sample agreed on the low attitudes of teachers in primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait towards the ethics of the profession in the field of education. Regarding the opinions of the respondents, the three best phrases were arranged as follows:

- * Teachers advocate inherent values within institutions to meet contemporary challenges .
 - .Teachers practically apply values by interacting with their students*
 - . Teachers discuss with their pupils about analyzing issues of value dimensions within schools*
- The following phrases occupied the last three places of the second question.
- . Teachers support students' attitudes toward embedding values*
 - . Teachers instruct their students to demonstrate ethics in primary schools*

Teachers use reward and punishment to establish values in schools .*

This confirms that the traditional method of teaching in directing and guiding students based on direct advice is no longer useful in the current era .

Axes 3: The effect of educational technology innovations and their impact on the value system within primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait

Table 8: Responses to Questionnaire Axes 3

m	Phrase	Always	frequently	Sometimes	Scarcely	not correct	K2	Significance level	Weighted	Direction	Relative	Arrangement
1	The innovations adversely affect the ethical pattern of elementary education in public education in the State of Kuwait	150 12,5%	230 19,2%	370 30,8%	280 23,3%	170 14,2%	3,383	001,0	2,92	Sometimes	58%	1
2	Technology is employed according to a specific methodology within primary schools in general education	200 16,7%	170 14,2%	250 20,8%	290 24,2%	290 24,2%	3,383	001,0	2,75	Sometimes	49%	4
3	There is an organized business plan for students' use of technology innovations within	140 11,7%	180 15%	240 20%	290 24,2%	350 29,2%	2,325	001,0	2,55	Scarcely	51%	9

	primary schools in general education											
4	The state finances the equipping of primary schools with public education in the State of Kuwait with technological innovations according to an ambitious development plan	170	170	250	330	280	2,230	001,0	2,66	Sometimes	53%	8
		14,2%	14,2%	20,8%	27,5%	23,3%						
5	The state supports the use of technology within public education schools as a major quality requirement	210	180	260	210	340	6,102	001,0	2,77	Sometimes	55%	3
		17,5%	15%	21,7%	17,05%	28,3%						
6	Educators employ technology advancements in schools with great skill	180	190	200	360	270	6,422	001,0	2,73	Sometimes	55%	5
		15%	15,8%	16,7%	30	22,5%						
7	Technological innovations affect communication and dialogue skills among students	160	210	230	260	340	1,55	001,0	2,66	Sometimes	53%	8
		13,3%	17,5%	19,2%	21,7%	28,3%						
8	Technological innovations support students' desire for self-learning	210	170	240	310	270	329	001,0	2,78	Sometimes	56%	2
		17,5%	14,2%	20%	25,8%	22,5%						
9	Technology innovations support the general trend of	180	180	200	360	280	8,136	001,0	2,68	Sometimes	54%	6
		15%	15%	16,7%	30%	23,3%						

	openness to the other												
10	Technological innovations in primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait are able to keep pace with global developments in the field of educational technology	210	180	200	220	390					Sometimes	53%	7
		17,5%	15%	16,7%	18,3%	32,5%	6,102	001,0	2,67				

Table (8) shows the results of the "K2" test to indicate the differences between the within public education schools in the State of Kuwait, where the values of "K2" ranged between (2,38 – 3,38). All of them are significant at the level of significance (0.001), which indicates the existence of statistically significant differences between the opinions of the study sample individuals.

The study sample members agreed that the impact of educational technology innovations and their impact on the values system within primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait negatively affects the ethical pattern of education. The general public in the State of Kuwait has the highest relative weight (58%) in a direction sometimes, and the employment of educational technology according to a specific methodology within elementary schools in general education has an impact on the values system with the lowest relative weight (49%).(The relative weight of these expressions ranged between (55.2) and (92.2) indicating that the participants agreed on the low impact of educational technology innovations and their impact on the value system within primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait. When the opinions of the sample are arranged according to the degree of importance , the best three phrases are as follows :

- * The innovations adversely affect the ethical pattern in primary schools in public education in the State of Kuwait .
- Technology innovations support students' desire for self-learning*
- * The state supports the use of technology in primary schools in public education as a major quality requirement.

Despite occupying the last three positions, the following statements confirm that there is no clear national vision regarding the employment of technology within the public education institutions in Kuwait that invests in the energies of teachers in shaping the ethics of the profession.

- * The state finances equipping primary schools with public education in the State of Kuwait with technological innovations according to an ambitious development plan, and technological innovations

affect communication and dialogue skills among students.
Technology is employed according to a specific methodology in primary schools.*

Axes 4: Requirements to support teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the education profession in light of the developments in educational technology and its impact on primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait .

Table 9 : Responses to Questionnaire Axes 4

m	Phrase	Strongly Agree	OK	To some extent	not agree	Strongly Disagree	K2	Significance level	Weighted average	Direction	Relative weight
1	Reinforcement of the value system within the primary stage institutions of public education in the State of Kuwait	400	250	310	160	80	6,381	001,0	3,60	ok	72%
		33,3%	20,8 %	25,8%	13,2%	6,67%					
2	Training teachers to employ modern technologies to enhance learning fun	240	410	250	190	110	6,422	001,0	3,4	ok	68%
		20%	34,2 %	20,8%	15,8%	9,2%					
3	Enabling students to use techniques to guide teachers to establish values	380	310	220	170	120	6,138	001,0	3,61	ok	72,5 %
		31,7%	25,8 %	18,3%	14,2%	10%					
4	Embedding values and ethics through modern										

	technological media to support professional ethics	400 33,3%	250 20,8%	220 18,3%	170 14,2%	160 13,3%	8,249	001,0	3,47	ok	69,4%
5	Embedding values and ethics through modern technological media to support professional ethics	310 25,8%	350 29,2%	250 20,8%	170 14,2%	120 10%	2,183	0001.0	3,51	ok	70,2%
6	Training teachers to use modern technologies through standardized training programs	250 20,8%	340 29,2%	430 35,8%	120 10%	60 5%	1,793	001,0	3,48	ok	69,6%
7	Training teachers to establish professional ethics through direct interviews and interviews	350 29,2%	310 25,8%	220 18,3%	190 15,8%	130 10,8%	1,460	001,0	3,46	ok	69,2%
8	Promote the general trend of the state towards adopting technology as a general approach to openness	400 33,3%	220 18,3%	250 20,8%	160 13,3%	170 14,3%	3,383	001,0	33,43	ok	68,6%
9	Building an ambitious national plan for technology employment in the framework of preserving the nation's identity	450 37,5%	300 25%	200 16,7%	150 12,5%	100 8,3%	6,102	001,0	3,7	ok	74%

Table 9 shows the results of the "K2" test which measures the differences between the opinions of the study sample members in the fourth axis expressions. **The axis expresses the requirements to support teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the education profession in light of the developments in education technology and its impact on primary school pupils general education in the State of**

Kuwait, The values ranged between (6,102 - 6,422) with a level of significance (0.001), which indicates that there are statistically significant differences between the opinions of the members of the study sample. **The members of the study sample also agreed that the requirements to support teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the education profession in the light of the developments in education technology And its effect on the primary stage of public education in the State of Kuwait** can be achieved by training teachers to employ modern technologies to enhance learning pleasure with the lowest relative weight (68%) in an appropriate direction, and by building an ambitious national plan for technical employment in the framework to preserve the nation's identity with the highest relative weight (74%) in the OK direction. The relative weight of these expressions ranged between (7.3) and (4.3), which highly indicates the agreement of the sample members on the importance of **such requirements**, and when arranged according to the degree of its importance in relation to the opinions of the sample, the ranking of the three highest phrases are as **follows**:

- * Building an ambitious national plan for the technical use of technology in the framework of preserving the nation's identity .
- Enabling students to use technology, which supports teachers to establish values .
- Strengthening the value system within the primary level institutions of public education in the State of Kuwait .

On the other hand, the following statement came last in terms of importance of participants opinions:

- Training teachers to establish professional ethics through direct interviews and interviews .
- Training teachers to employ modern technologies to enhance learning pleasure.

This confirms that the national trend towards technology investment to support the ethics of the profession must be the direction of the state, and direct clear strategic planning towards supporting ethics within primary schools in the public education in the State of Kuwait .

Recommendations

After reviewing the theoretical and field framework of the study, the study recommends the following :

- * Training primary school teachers in general education in Kuwait to meet the challenges of the contemporary technological revolution.
- . Promoting teachers' attitudes towards the ethics of the teaching profession*
- * Supporting teachers in building effective and meaningful dialogue with their students and in abstaining from violence and strength.
- * Promoting directions of dialogue, understanding and participation among primary school students in public education in the State of Kuwait.
- Equipping the students with the use of technology safely*
- * Organizing discussion and debates between teachers and management to discuss matters related to professional ethics and accountability.

* Supporting educational activities that support the national identity of primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait to adapt the challenges of globalization and technology.

* Enabling teachers to communicate with the parents of the students to build bridges of trust between them in what is in the best interest of their students and ensuring their good educational communication.

* Purifying technological innovations from everything that negatively affect students' values and morals.

* Supporting teachers' attitudes towards higher studies in the field of moral empowerment and identity support in the Kuwaiti society to face technology challenges.

* Analyzing the attitudes of primary school pupils in general education in the State of Kuwait towards the use of technology and building a strategic vision to enhance employment.

* Reviewing, and evaluating practices and attitudes toward professional ethics within primary schools in primary education.

* Honoring ideal teachers who support ethical trends in light of the technological revolution in the elementary stage of public education in the State of Kuwait.

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